

IMPORTANT AND PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract: This article examines the essence and content of the new paradigm of the education system, its basic principles, as well as the features of personality-oriented learning. The content of the concept of the system-activity approach in its correlation with the innovative strategy of education was revealed.

Keywords: education, paradigm, innovative education, systematic-activity method, civilizational approach, human development.

The current stage of development of society is characterized by the complexity of social processes. The interaction of the information civilization that was forming in it by the 10th-11th centuries, the industrial civilization that has not yet lost its significance, and, therefore, the characteristics of local civilizations that reflect the peculiarities of regions, creates difficulties in explaining social processes. The transition from one stage of system development to another is determined by the intensification of chaotic states, in the words of the interdisciplinary doctrine of synergeticism - an increase in entropy. [4] The technological revolution that arose under the influence of the development of production literally gave humanity a choice: to live together as a whole system or to collapse. The preservation of humanity as a whole, sustainably developing system requires the development of new mechanisms, and it is becoming increasingly clear that the basis of this mechanism should be the human resource, its spiritual potential.

The participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan as an element of the global community in this process also creates certain difficulties. In our country, the general civilizational processes are combined with the issues of the restoration of our national statehood, the construction of a democratic state in our country, the development of a national model of civil society. In this regard, a "new strategy" of development has been developed - a path to achieving sustainable evolutionary development of Uzbekistan, the harmonization of universal human principles with our national identity. [1] The correctness of the path we have chosen and our goals is confirmed by the peaceful and stable development of our country in the current digital era. This development considers the expansion of a person and his freedoms as the criterion for the development of society. The concept of human development, which is currently widely promoted by the entire world community, considers the development of education in direct connection with the fulfillment of its tasks.

The changes currently taking place in the Republic of Uzbekistan require the creation of socio-pedagogical conditions that are compatible with these processes and require the implementation of a new model of education, both of thoughtful reform, creative design. This requires a corps of teachers with a new analytical, design-constructive nature of thinking, aimed at improving the pedagogical paradigm. In other words, solving the problems of higher education is impossible without raising the pedagogical intellectual culture, without actively influencing social thought, and without conditionally eliminating the stereotypes and conservatism formed in the science and practice of pedagogy. The solution to these problems is directly related to the development of innovative educational technologies of teaching. Therefore, the logic of a person-centered innovative model should be directed from: estimating the goals of education (what and why?) to selecting and designing the content (what?), organizing the learning process (how?), choosing teaching methods and tools (with what?),

taking into account the level of teacher qualification (who is teaching?) and diagnosing the achieved results of education (what did we get?). From this point of view, the goal of education is realized with the help of a pedagogical system, which is considered as an element of a “large system” called education, and it should be provided in a way based on the “general law of balance”. Such an approach necessitates the idea of inserting educational institutions into a “highly responsible educational environment”. The recognition of education by the economic, social and cultural spheres allows us to move from slogans and theoretical thinking to the construction of new effective educational systems that meet the needs of both the individual and society and its economy. A healthy society is built on citizens who are formed by receiving the knowledge they deserve.

Human-centered education primarily means a change in the educational paradigm. If earlier, during the time of Herbert and Pestalozzi, and later during the industrial revolution, the educational system gave priority to teaching activities, now, in the post-industrial stage, in the era of its informationization, priority is given to learning activities. Therefore, the old paradigm: teacher-textbook-student is being replaced by a new paradigm: student-textbook-teacher. The teacher is acquiring a new status, which, we believe, is still important, but will take on a different form. The task of the teacher now is to organize the independent cognitive activity of the student, to teach him to independently acquire knowledge and apply the acquired knowledge in practice. To achieve these goals, the teacher should choose teaching methods that not only give students the opportunity to master ready-made knowledge, but also help them independently acquire knowledge from various sources, help them form their own views, argue for them, and use previously acquired knowledge as a method for acquiring new knowledge.

The methodologically important political aspect of the development of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the need to preserve the continuity and integrity of the educational sphere. Its relevance is especially evident in the aspect of continuing education. Continuing education is considered as an alternative to the previously existing discrete system, its humanistically oriented constitution and a leading method for reforming education. That is, we need to move from the principle of “knowledge for a lifetime” (obrazovanie na vsyu zhizn) to the principle of “knowledge throughout life” (obrazovanie cherez vsyu zhizn). In the new edition of the Law “On Education”, adopted in 2000, continuing education is considered as a pedagogical system, which is interpreted as a whole complex of forms, methods, means, and ways of expanding and deepening general knowledge, social maturity and professional competence.[2] In the process of developing human qualities, an important task of the education system is to help its students move from vague paths to clear concepts, to cultivate reflection, to create the ability to creatively and freely organize the flow of feelings, memories and ideas. Education should give students a taste for truth, the art of searching for it, and positive experience. The goal of education is therefore to view truth as a necessary and achievable basis, but requiring labor, courage, and perseverance, and to view knowledge not as a source of illumination, but as the result of “continuous thinking”.

Education is a process of achieving a certain goal based on the subjective-objective actions of teachers and students. The educational process is characterized by the achievements of goal-oriented steps, stages, which are determined by the goals of education. As a qualitative description, education is the result of the state, society and human mastery of values in the process of educational activity, which are significant for the economic, moral, intellectual state of all consumers of the product of the educational sphere - the state, society and each person. From a procedural point of view, education means the activity of a growing person in a specially organized environment, which is motivated by knowledge, which is continuously

enriched with new complex educational material. The content of higher professional education is based on the concept of a systematic-activity method. [3] “Systematic-activity method” includes two meanings: “systematic method” and “activity method”. “Systemic method” is a collective term that refers to methodological directions that have emerged from various specific disciplines and consider the study of their objects as systems integrated into a single whole. The basis of this method is the rejection of one-sided analytical, linear-causal methods of research, focusing on the totality of the integrated qualities of the object, their origin. Therefore, attention is paid to identifying the relationship and connections within the object itself, with the environment. Definitions close to the term “system” are related to “structure”, “environment”. If the term “system” means the integrity of the object, then “structure” indicates its internal discreteness assembled from parts, their mutual communication and mutual relations. Based on this, they form a whole. The term “structure” is revealed through “element”, “connections” and “relations”.

Based on the term "activity method", it is necessary to plan the content of study subjects and practice based on comprehensive consideration of the future socio-productive activity of the graduate of the educational institution. From a psychological point of view, an active method of the learning process can be considered as a manifestation of the specific features of the process of human assimilation of the culture accumulated by mankind, the transfer to a person of the general historical experience developed by social practice: knowledge, skills, abilities, types and methods of activity. This process is carried out in the form of cooperation, joint activity of the teacher and the student. The teacher organizes the cognitive activity of the student in accordance with the goals of education using didactic tools. Collaborative activity can have various forms: from direct contact with each person to "communication with humanity": his experience, tools of labor, scientific achievements, works of art, etc. During cognitive activity, the learner acquires knowledge, skills, and intellectual abilities, and accumulates a certain experience of socio-psychological competence.

So, the intended content of teaching as an element of the pedagogical system requires the following: the selection of educational material should be carried out in accordance with the completeness and systematicity of the types of activity, which is necessary for the development of a person's intellectual skills, for the acquisition of professionally qualified skills necessary for performing the main types of activity at different levels of difficulty. When planning the content of the desired subject, we must take into account the fact that each of the subjects mastered by students should have its own fundamental impact on their general professional knowledge. That is, we must not forget that the principle of teaching not a subject, but a specialty should be maintained. As a strategic goal, we must direct all subjects to the study of phenomena and processes in a holistic manner. Such a holistic approach forms the human and professional qualities of a specialist.

The content of higher education, in addition to professionally oriented knowledge, should provide health, rational meaning - vital, practical wisdom, the ability to see the consequences of actions, to distinguish significant from random in behavior, to choose a solution that brings real benefit from possible options. Education is both in science and in art. It teaches people of different ages to understand the difficulties and problems encountered in life, gives them the means to overcome and solve them. We cannot achieve a high level of professional education - creative skills - without general humanitarian knowledge and innovative methods for solving the desired problems (socio-economic, production-technological, economic, etc.). An orientation towards these strategic directions has been adopted, but it can be said that conservatism regarding higher education has not yet been completely eliminated.

The implementation of these methods required the development of a new educational paradigm, primarily aimed at the development of spirituality and the creative basis of man. In this case, the most important task of educational practice is not only to teach the laws of nature and society, but also to coordinate relations in the “man-nature-society” system and arm oneself with a humanistic methodology for creative transformation of the world.

The main content of the new educational paradigm is to consider the preservation and development of the creative potential of man as the main goal of innovative education. But today, creativity and planning alone are not enough. Education must be imbued with universal human values. For this, first of all, it must develop balanced thinking based on the unity of man’s inner freedom and his social responsibility, tolerance for different thinking.

Innovative educational strategy provides for the systematic organization of the management of the educational process. Its first characteristic feature is that the teacher or the person organizing the training remains the leading element, but his position in relation to the student, to himself, changes. The teacher is not only considered as a keeper and supplier of subject knowledge, a source of information, norms and programs, but also acts as an assistant in the formation and development of the student's personality (independent of the student's level of knowledge, understanding or lack of understanding). The nature of management, influencing the student changes. The authoritarian position of power, the right of the strong disappears, and is replaced by a position of cooperation, assistance, inspiration, increased attention to the student, democratic interaction in the formation and development of a person. The student's position changes from mastering the result, from the received assessment to actively interacting with the teacher and his fellow students. [5]

As a second characteristic feature, we can consider changes in the functions of the knowledge mastered in higher education institutions and in the methods of organizing the process of its reception. In our time, knowledge has become the "third social force" after wealth and power, allowing a person to take his place in modern culture and civilization. But it must be given only in the values of the modern information society, that is, in a systematic, interdisciplinary, generalized type. The nature of the mastery of knowledge begins to lose its reproductive, purely memorizing character and is organized in various forms of thought activity, which is sought as a process of productive creativity.

The third characteristic feature is the prioritization of the social nature of education and the development of the person. This is reflected in the orientation of education not to individual, but to group forms of education, to cooperative activities, to various forms of interaction, to interpersonal relationships, to the emergence of individuality from the “collective subject”, to the constant co-creation of joy. As educational issues related to the content of this priority innovative strategy, the task of training the organizers, technologists of the educational process, and pedagogues is considered first of all. Training (upgrading, retraining) of teachers should put forward three main goals:

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